

THE
SALTICIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA
Part 3 He-Iran

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Heliocapensis termitophagus © Vida van der Walt

THE SALTICIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA PART 3 (HE-IRAN)

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The family Salticidae is the largest spider family and is known from 689 genera and 6809 species. From South Africa, 85 genera and 363 species are known (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The Salticidae Guides are arranged into seven volumes, of which this is Part 3:

Part 1: *Aelurillus* to *Dendryphantas* 41 species (63 pp.)

Part 2: *Euophrys* to *Hasarius* 49 species (65 pp.)

Part 3: *Heliophanus* to *Iranattus* 73 species (74 pp.)

Part 4: *Kima* to *Mogrus* 51 species (66 pp.)

Part 5: *Myrmarachne* to *Pignus* 53 species (66 pp.)

Part 6: *Planamarengo* to *Tanzania* 55 species (60 spp.)

Part 7: *Tenuiballus* to *Zulunigma* 58 species (66 pp.).

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GENUS *HELAFRICANUS* Wesolowska, 1986

The genus *Helafricanus* Wesolowska, 1986 is known from 46 species (World Spider Catalog, 2025). It was elevated from a subgenus of *Heliophanus* C. L. Koch, 1833 by Wesolowska (2024). Fourteen species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Helafricanus patellaris* (Simon, 1901)

MORPHOLOGY: Small to medium-sized spiders, measuring 2.5–4.5 mm. Males: carapace black, in some species with a thin, whitish median streak; abdomen black, usually with a white leaf-like pattern or a median stripe, sometimes also featuring a thin white line along the lateral edges of the body. Females have mottled brown and black colouration and an abdominal pattern comprising a light central stripe composed of several pairs of merging spots. Notably, some males exhibit an abdominal pattern similar to females (e.g., *H. demonstrativus*). Light streaks/patches are composed of white hairs. The diagnostic character of *Helafricanus* males is the presence of a large palpal patellar apophysis. The structure of the female genital organs is similar in all congeners: the copulatory openings are usually placed at the posterior part of the epigyne.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living spiders found on the ground or plants, and collected from a broad range of habitats.

TAXONOMY: The genus *Helafricanus* was elevated from a subgenus of *Heliophanus* C. L. Koch, 1833 by Wesolowska (2024).

Figs 1–4. *Helafricanus* spp. 1. Female. 2. Male. 3. Male, general appearance. 4. Female, abdominal markings. Credits: 1. Bruce Blake. 2. Peter Webb. 3, 4. Wesolowska (2024).

Helafricanus bisulcus (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Intertidal Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1986 from Cape Town. Known also from Namibia. In South Africa known from several localities around Cape Town (EOO= 4 744 km²; AOO= 20 km²; 7–71 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in southern Africa the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Western Cape:** Cape Agulhas (-34.82, 19.99); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.47, 19.27); Jacobsbaai (-33.15, 18.03); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Table Mountain National Park: Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38); Yzerfontein (-33.37, 18.16).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers. Some specimens were found in the intertidal zone along rocky seashores. They were found nested in crevices in rocks close to the seashore, as well as nesting in a succulent *Salicornia*, a dominant vegetation component along rocky shores (Fig. 6). Sampled from the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024) and Fernkloof Nature Reserve (Hamilton-Atwell & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. It is a senior synonym of *Heliophanus villosus* Wesołowska, 1986. Redescribed by Haddad & Wesołowska (2013) and now placed in *Helafricanus* (Wesołowska, 2024).

Figs 1–9. *Helafricanus bisulcus*. 1, 2, 5. Female. 3, 4. Male. 6. Nests in succulent *Salicornia*. 7, 8. Epigyne. 9. Male palp. Credits: 1–4. Vida van der Walt. 5, 7. Charles Haddad. 6. Victor Hamilton-Atwell. 8, 9. From Haddad & Wesołowska (2013).

Helafricanus debilis (Simon, 1901)

COMMON NAME: Common Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1901 from Kimberley, South Africa. A common species known from ten African countries. In South Africa, it has a wide range and is known from all the provinces (EOO=841 195 km²; AOO=276 km²; 3–1836 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cala (-31.52, 27.68); Port St Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein district, Deelhoek farm (-28.83, 26.08); Bloemfontein district, Hopefield farm (-28.90, 26.23); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit (-25.80, 28.74); Faerie Glen Nature Reserve Pretoria (-25.77, 28.30); Hammanskraal (-25.41, 28.27); Irene, field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23); Kliprivierberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Pretoria, Arcadia (-25.74, 28.22); Pretoria, Hazelwood (-25.77, 28.25); Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Hell's Gate Military Base (-28.01, 32.44); Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ithala Game Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Midlands, Boston, Good Hope plantation (-29.65, 29.97); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Newcastle district, Ncandu Falls (-27.85, 29.83); Newcastle district, Moorfield farm (-27.52, 29.43); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); 15 km N Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Wakefield farm (-29.47, 29.89). **Limpopo:** Goro Game Ranch (-22.94, 29.43); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64); Medike Mountain Reserve (-22.99, 29.61); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29).

Figs 1–7. *Helafricanus debilis*. 1–2, 5. Female. 3–4. Male. 6. Male palp. 7. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2. Vida van der Walt. 3–5. Peter Webb. 6–7. From Wesolowska (1986).

Helaffricanus debilis (continued)

Mpumalanga: Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Kruger National Park, Satara, N'wanetsi (-24.44, 31.88); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-24.98, 31.59); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Magoebaskloof (-23.87, 30.01); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Potchefstroom (-26.70, 27.09); Ventersdorp (-26.32, 26.82); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **North-east Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Vaalharts Scheme (-27.77, 24.77). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Elgin (-34.16, 19.06); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.47, 19.27); Goukamma Nature Reserve (-34.03, 22.55); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.87, 22.48); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Table Mountain National Park, Cecilia (-34.00, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: A free-living plant-dweller. Specimens were occasionally collected from low-growing herbaceous plants and from rocks and logs on the ground surface. In South Africa, it has been sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). Also sampled from agroecosystems such as cotton and pistachio (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). In Ndumo Game Reserve, the species was frequently collected from bark of the fever tree *Vachellia xanthophloea* along various pans and floodplains, where silk retreats were constructed beneath the bark structure (Haddad, 2016). Adults were occasionally seen foraging on the tree trunks.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. It is found in more than 20 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesolowska (1986), redescribed by Haddad & Wesolowska (2009). Listed as *Helaffricanus* by Wesolowska (2024).

Figs 1–2. *Helaffricanus debilis*. 1. Female. 2. Male. Credits: Peter Webb.

Helafricanus demonstrativus (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1986 from East London in the Eastern Cape. In South Africa, it is known from six provinces, including eight protected areas (EOO=484 364 km²; AOO=80 km²; 1–1744 m a.s.l.). Recorded from six African countries. Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Lesotho, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Fort Beaufort (-32.78, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90). **Free State:** Memel (-27.69, 29.56). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Newcastle district, Moorfield farm (-27.52, 29.43); Newcastle district, Normandien farms (-27.55, 29.49); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Meetsa-A-Bophelo Mission Station (-24.25, 30.45); Politsi (-23.76, 30.09); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park Skukuza (-24.98, 31.59); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers found on vegetation and in litter in the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). Occasionally sampled from rocks.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. It is found in more than eight protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska, 1986), with data added by Wesołowska (2003). Placed in *Helafricanus* by Wesołowska (2024).

Figs 1–9. *Helafricanus demonstrativus*. 1–3. Female. 4, 5. Male. 6, 7. Epigyne. 8, 9. Male palp. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3, 4, 6, 8. Charles Haddad. 5, 7, 9. From Wesołowska (2003).

Helafricanus fascinatus (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Fascinating Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1986 from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species is known from five African countries. In South Africa, it is known from four provinces (EOO=311 669 km²; AOO=32 km²; 47–1730 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range of the species, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Rwanda, South Africa, Sudan and Yemen, and possibly introduced to Switzerland.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof, Ferndale, Keurkloof farm (-33.68, 24.83). **Free State:** Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Kliprivierberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mkuzi Swamp road (-27.01, 32.51); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers sampled from grasses and low herbs in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They make silk retreats in leaf litter (Fig. 2) and low foliage. In the Ndumo Game Reserve, it was sampled from the bark of the fever tree (Haddad, 2016). It was also sampled from potato fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. It is protected in the Baviaanskloof (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023), Free State National Botanical Gardens and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006; Haddad, 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska, 1986). Redescribed by Wesołowska & Haddad (2009) and now listed in *Helafricanus* (Wesołowska 2024).

Figs 1–9. *Helafricanus fascinatus*. 1, 2. Male. 3. Female. 4. Retreat. 5, 6. Male palp. 7–9. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 4. Ruan Booysen. 2, 3, 6, 8, 9. Charles Haddad. 5, 7. From Wesołowska & Haddad (2009).

Helafricanus hastatus (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1986 from Melville Koppies in Gauteng. The species is known from Lesotho and South Africa. In South Africa, it has been recorded from seven provinces (EOO=386 315 km²; AOO=136 km²; 6–2799 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Baviaanskloof, Ferndale, Keurkloof farm (-33.68, 24.83); Cala (-31.52, 27.68); Fort Fordyce Forest Reserve (-32.69, 26.51); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89). **Free State:** Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.20); Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.28, 29.20); Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48, 29.01); Vaal Dam (-26.90, 28.12). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Krugersdorp, Kromdraai (-25.58, 27.47); Melville Koppies (-26.17, 27.99); Rietveldam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Champagne Castle (-29.08, 29.35); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Howick, Lions River (-29.47, 30.20); Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.35, 30.64); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); Newcastle district, Normandien farms (-27.55, 29.49); Newcastle district, Moorfield farm (-27.52, 29.43); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63). **Mpumalanga:** Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Loskop Research Station (-25.17, 29.40); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Waterval Boven (-25.63, 30.32). **North West:** Potchefstroom (-26.70, 27.09); Thabela Thabeng Mountain Retreat (-26.86, 28.30).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers found on vegetation in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled in crops such as cotton, kenaf and sorghum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it has been sampled from >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Both sexes are known (Wesołowska, 1986). Redescribed by Wesołowska (2003) and placed in *Helafricanus* by Wesołowska (2024).

Figs 1–6. *Helafricanus hastatus*. 1. Female. 2–4. Male. 5. Male palp. 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Peter Webb. 3, 4. Vida van der Walt. 5, 6. From Wesołowska and Haddad (2013).

Helafricanus insperatus (Wesolowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1986 from Magaliesberg, Gauteng. It is known from four African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from four provinces (EOO=421 938 km²; AOO=72 km²; 290–1414 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (-25.77, 28.30); Leeufontein Nature Reserve (-25.38, 28.64); Magaliesberg (-25.99, 27.54); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **Limpopo:** Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Nylstroom/Modimolle (-24.69, 28.40); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Numbi (-25.12, 31.20); Kruger National Park, Satara (-24.52, 31.77); Marble Hall (-25.09, 29.09); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.49, 21.08); Elgin (-34.16, 19.06); Gondwana Game Reserve (-34.07, 21.90); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: The species has been sampled by beating and sweeping vegetation in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). The species was also sampled from citrus, cotton and kenaf (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it has been recorded from nine protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska, 1986, 2003) and now placed in *Helafricanus* (Wesolowska, 2024).

Helafricanus insperatus
(Wesolowska, 1986)

Figs 1–10. *Heliophanus insperatus*. 1–4. Female from Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve. 5, 6. Male palp. 7. Male palpal femur. 8. Abdomen. 9, 10. Epigyne. Credits: 1–4. Peter Webb. 5, 9. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 6–8, 10. From Wesolowska (1986).

Helafricanus marshalli (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)

COMMON NAME: Marshall's Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 1903 and known only from the Durban area (EOO=500 km^2; AOO=8 km^2; 17 m a.s.l.). Due to its small range, the status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Kloof, near Durban (-29.78, 30.83).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesolowska (1986) and now listed as *Helafricanus* (Wesolowska 2024). The species is larger than other congeners and has dark legs with yellow tarsi (Peckham & Peckham, 1903).

Figs 1–3. *Helafricanus marshalli*. 1. Male palp. 2. Male palpal femur. 3. Male palpal tibia. From Wesolowska (1986).

Helaffricanus modicus (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)

COMMON NAME: Eastern Cape Helaffricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1903 from Willowmore in the Eastern Cape. The species is presently known from three African countries. In South Africa, it has been sampled from three provinces (EOO=317 609 km²; AOO=108 km²; 7–2398 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, Madagascar and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Citrus Research Station (-33.55, 25.69); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Cradock (-32.16, 25.61); East London, Pineapple Research Station (-33.02, 27.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Kirkwood (-33.39, 25.43); Lady Grey (-30.71, 27.20); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Willowmore (-33.30, 23.50). **Free State:** Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.49, 21.08); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.47, 19.27); Jacobsbaai (-33.15, 18.03); Laingsburg District, Wagendrift Lodge (-33.38, 20.94); Montagu Baths (-33.77, 20.12); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Rawsonville (-33.70, 19.34); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.36, 21.69); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

LIFESTYLE: A free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled from crops such as lucerne and in vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it has been sampled from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesolowska (1986) and now placed in *Helaffricanus* (Wesolowska 2024).

Figs 1–8. *Helaffricanus modicus*. 1, 2, 4. Female. 3, 5. Male. 6, 7. Male palp. 8. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3. Linda Wiese. 4–6. Charles Haddad. 7, 8. From Wesolowska (1986).

Helaffricanus nanus (Wesołowska, 2003)

COMMON NAME: Small Helaffricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described from Swartrus in the Free State. The species is also known from Namibia. In South Africa it is known from seven provinces (EOO= 343 477 km²; AOO= 120 km²; 565–2329 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.04, 24.94). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein district, Hopefield farm (-28.90, 26.23); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Fauresmith district, Boschrand farm (-29.93, 24.80); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); Luckhoff district, Bankfontein farm (-29.73, 24.77); Norvalspont (-30.63, 25.48); Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.27, 29.20); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93); Soetdoring Nature Reserve (-29.05, 26.21); Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48, 29.01); Swartrus (-27.75, 25.50); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Gauteng:** Kameeldrift (-25.66, 28.32); Meyerton (-26.55, 28.01); Pretoria, Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (-25.77, 28.30); Pretoria, Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **Limpopo:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **Mpumalanga:** Badplaas (-25.95, 30.56); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Waterval Boven (-25.63, 30.32). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.68, 27.79); Rob Ferriera Nature Reserve (-25.13, 27.57). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.56, 24.16).

LIFESTYLE: A plant-dwelling species collected from grasses and shrubs in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Thicket biomes. The species was also found in cotton, potato and tomato fields and pecan nuts orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats and sampled in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska, 2003) and listed in *Helaffricanus* by Wesołowska (2024).

Figs 1–5. *Helaffricanus nanus*. 1. Female. 2. Female eye pattern. 3. Male. 4. Male palp. 5. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3. Peter Webb. 4, 5. From Wesołowska (2003).

Helafricanus patellaris (Simon, 1901)

COMMON NAME: Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1901 with the type locality only given as Cape Colony. The species has also been sampled from Lesotho. In South Africa, it is known from seven provinces (EOO=922 802 km²; AOO=92 km²; 5–2452 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52). **Free State:** Luckhoff district, Bankfontein farm (-29.73, 24.77); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13). **Gauteng:** Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Wakefield farm (-29.47, 29.89). **Mpumalanga:** Kaapsehoop (-25.56, 30.78); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Northern Cape:** Alexander Bay (-28.60, 16.49); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Oryx Game farm (-28.41, 22.17). **Western Cape:** Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Cape Town, Claremont (-33.98, 18.47); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.42, 19.23); Laingsburg District, Wagendrift Lodge (-33.37, 20.94); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Table Mountain National Park, Devil's Peak (-33.92, 18.45).

LIFESTYLE: A species found in a wide range of habitats, including from under rocks, in leaf litter, grasses and on the walls of buildings. It was also sampled from maize fields in Lesotho. In South Africa, it has been sampled from the Nama Karoo, Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024) and Grassland biomes (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. It is protected in five protected areas, i.e. the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009), Fernkloof Nature Reserve (Hamilton-Atwell & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023), Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024) and Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Information added by Wesolowska (1986) and Wesolowska & Haddad (2014). Now placed in *Helafricanus* (Wesolowska, 2024).

Figs 1–11. *Helafricanus patellaris*. 1, 2, 4. Female. 3, 5, 8. Male. 6, 7. Male palp. 9. Female abdomen. 10, 11. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2. Vida van der Walt. 3. Peter Webb. 4, 5, 7, 10. Charles Haddad. 6, 11. From Wesolowska & Haddad (2014). 8, 9. From Wesolowska (2024).

Helaffricanus pauper (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Pauper Helaffricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1986 from Kenya. It is known from both sexes. The species has been recorded from five African countries. In South Africa, it is known from four provinces (EOO=286 829 km²; AOO=28 km²; 47–1556 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ethiopia, Kenya, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dlinza Forest, near Eshowe (-28.89, 31.45); Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Ithala Game Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers sampled from the Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range in the eastern half of South Africa, although sporadic, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in two reserves, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Additional data on the male was added by Wesołowska (1999, 2003) and it was placed in *Helaffricanus* by Wesołowska (2024).

Figs 1–7. *Helaffricanus pauper*. 1–4. Female. 5. Male palp. 6. Male palpal femur. 7. Epigyne. Credits: 1–4. Vida van der Walt. 5–7. From Wesołowska (1986).

Helafricanus pistaciae (Wesołowska, 2003)

COMMON NAME: Pistachio Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2003 from Prieska in South Africa and also sampled from Zimbabwe. It has a wide distribution in South Africa and has been sampled in seven provinces (EOO=594 324 km²; AOO=188 km²; 47–1795 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Kroonstad district, Doornkloof farm (-27.72, 27.70); Luckhof district, Bankfontein farm (-29.73, 24.77); Swartrus (-27.75, 25.50); Willem Pretorius Game Reserve (-28.28, 27.20). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.68, 28.94); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-25.36, 27.99); Rooideplaatsdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.42, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.35, 30.60); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Acacia Lodge Game Reserve (-24.56, 27.37); Dendron, Amsterdam farm (-23.37, 29.32); Maasstroom (-22.75, 28.43); Magoebaskloof (-23.87, 30.01); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.70); Nylstroom/Modimolle (-24.69, 28.40); Ratombo Forest (-23.06, 30.17); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Soutpansberg, Stoke farm (-22.48, 29.88); Thabazimbi (-24.60, 27.38); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Zanzibar Border Post (-22.57, 28.45). **Mpumalanga:** Dennilton (-25.30, 29.18); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Verena (-25.50, 29.02); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Rustenburg (-25.70, 27.30); Thabela Thabeng Mountain Retreat (-26.86, 27.30); Ventersdorp (-26.32, 26.80). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.30, 24.81); Colesburg district, Vogelsfontein farm (-30.62, 25.30); Kakamas, Die Mas (-28.76, 20.61); Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska district, Remhoogte farm (-29.52, 23.00); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.56, 24.16).

Figs 1–11. *Helafricanus pistaciae*. 1, 6. Female. 2–5, 7. Male. 8, 9. Male palp. 10, 11. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 5. Peter Webb. 2–4. Vida van der Walt. 6, 7, 9, 11. Charles Haddad. 8, 10. From Wesołowska (2003).

Helaffricanus pistaciae (continued)

LIFESTYLE: This species is an agrobiont spider sampled from pistachio orchards at the type locality, Green Valley Nuts in the Prieska district of the Northern Cape. It dominated the arboreal fauna and was also common in ground covers (Haddad & Louw, 2006). It was also sampled from several other agroecosystems: cotton, kenaf, pecan orchards, potatoes, pumpkin and sugar cane (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Most of the records presented here were collected by pitfall trapping, beating, canopy fogging or sweep-netting, suggesting fairly adaptable habits. The species was found from low herbaceous plants and on the ground up to tree canopies in the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska, 2003). Now placed in *Helaffricanus* (Wesołowska, 2024).

Figs 1–2. *Helaffricanus pistaciae*. 1. Female. 2. Male. Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Helafricanus proszynskii (Wesołowska, 2003)

COMMON NAME: Proszynski's Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2003 from Bredasdorp in the Western Cape. Also sampled from Lesotho. In South Africa, it is known from eight provinces (EOO=769 304 km²; AOO=128 km²; 7–2398 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cala (-31.52, 27.68); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Maclear, Prentjiesberg (-31.12, 28.18); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein district, Deelhoek farm (-28.83, 26.08); Coalbrook (-26.85, 27.87); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62); Kestell (-28.31, 28.70); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Petrusburg (-29.11, 25.43); Reddersburg (-29.64, 26.15); Tusen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Vrede, Moreson (-27.52, 29.10). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Makatini Flats (-27.25, 32.22); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Waterval Boven (-25.63, 30.32). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.30, 24.81). **Western Cape:** Bredasdorp (-34.53, 20.04); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Table Mountain National Park, Tokai South (-34.07, 18.40).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). It was also sampled from cotton, tomato and wheat fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is conserved in nine protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska, 2003). Additional data added by Wesołowska & Haddad (2009). Now listed in *Helafricanus* (Wesołowska, 2024).

Figs 1–8. *Helafricanus proszynskii*. 1. Female, dorsal. 2. Female, eye pattern. 3, 6. Male, dorsal habitus. 4, 7, 8. Male palp. 5. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3. Peter Webb. 4, 5. From Wesołowska (2003). 6–8. Charles Haddad.

Helafricanus trepidus (Simon, 1910)

COMMON NAME: Namibia's Helafricanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1910 from Namibia. The species has been recorded from five African countries. In South Africa, it is known from eight provinces (EOO=743 358 km²; AOO=92 km²; 6–1444 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein district, Hopefield farm (-28.90, 26.23). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspruit (-25.80, 28.74); Dinokeng (-25.40, 28.38); Irene, field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Tswaing Nature Reserve, Tswaing farm (-25.41, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Lake St. Lucia (-28.00, 32.48); Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.60, 32.02); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Pafuri, Waller's Camp (-22.42, 30.91). **Mpumalanga:** Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Northern Cape:** Oryx Game farm (-28.41, 22.17); Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77). **Western Cape:** Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85).

LIFESTYLE: The species was sampled from shrubs and trees from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). In the Ndumo Game Reserve, it was collected from the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* (Haddad, 2016). The species was also recorded from agroecosystems such as cotton and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is conserved in 10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesolowska & Cumming (2008), with data added by Wesolowska & Haddad (2014). Now placed in *Helafricanus* (Wesolowska, 2024).

Figs 1–10. *Helafricanus trepidus* 1–4. Female. 5. Female abdomen. 6. Male. 7, 8. Male palp. 9, 10. Epigyne. Credits 1–3. Peter Webb. 4, 6, 8, 10. Charles Haddad. 5, 7, 9. From Wesolowska & Cumming (2008).

GENUS *HELIOCAPENSIS* Wesolowska, 1986

The genus *Heliocapensis* Wesolowska, 1986 is known from 13 species, of which 10 occur in South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

COMMON NAME: Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Heliocapensis peckhami* (Simon, 1902)

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders, 3.0–4.5 mm. Males are black, with an abdomen featuring a thin white line along the anterior margin and two or three pairs of small, round, or diagonal white spots. These spots are composed of white hairs or small scales, and spiders lose them as they age. Males have a very short embolus located at the tip of the bulb and the palpal tibia is often wider at its distal end. A white streak composed of small scales runs along the dorsal surface of the palpal cymbium. The female's epigyne is short and wide with a V-shaped posterior border. The internal structure of the epigyne is simple; the copulatory openings are placed laterally, the seminal ducts run posteriorly and towards the center of the epigyne, accessory glands are present, and they connect to the ducts before the oval spermathecae.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living spiders found on the ground or plant-dwellers collected from various habitat types.

DISTRIBUTION: Representatives of *Heliocapensis* occur in the Afrotropical Region. The ranges of most species are limited to the southern part of the continent.

TAXONOMY: The genus *Heliocapensis* was elevated from a subgenus of *Heliophanus* C. L. Koch, 1833 by Wesolowska (2024).

Heliocapensis sp. with prey. Credit: Bruce Blake.

Heliocapensis: General appearance of male and female. From Wesolowska (2024).

Heliocapensis aberdarensis (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Aberdare Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1986 from Kenya. Also sampled from South Africa. It is possibly undersampled and is expected to occur in more countries in between. In South Africa, it is known from five provinces, including six protected areas (EOO= 160 342 km²; AOO= 40 km²; 37–2204 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); 15 km ENE of Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52). **Free State:** Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62); Harrismith, Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.28, 29.20). **Gauteng:** Pretoria, Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (-25.77, 28.30); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-26.50, 28.25). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Midlands, Boston, Good Hope Plantation (-29.65, 29.97); Newcastle district, Moorfield farm (-27.87, 29.70); Royal Natal National Park (-28.73, 28.92). **Mpumalanga:** Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23).

LIFESTYLE: Recorded from alpine grasslands in East Africa. In South Africa it occurs on grasses and short shrubs in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020), Golden Gate Highlands National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024), Platberg Nature Reserve, Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023), Royal Natal National Park and Loskop Dam Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Female describe by Wesołowska (1986). Male added by Wesołowska and Haddad (2013). Now placed in *Heliocapensis* (Wesołowska (2024)).

Figs 1–8. *Heliocapensis aberdarensis*. 1, 2. Female. 3–5. Male. 6, 7. Male palp. 8. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2. Peter Webb. 3–5. Vida van der Walt. 6–8. From Wesołowska and Haddad (2013).

Heliocapensis bellus (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Clanwilliam Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1986 from Sneeuberg near Clanwilliam. The species is known only from two localities (EOO=500 km^2; AOO=4 km^2; 78 m a.s.l.). Due to its small range, the status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Clanwilliam, Sneeuberg (-32.16, 18.89); Darling (-33.37, 18.39).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male. Male carapace dark brown; abdomen dark brown with a few white scales on the anterior margin and only traces of white spots dorsally; leg I dark brown, with yellow metatarsi and tarsi, remaining legs pale brown (Wesołowska, 1986). Placed in *Heliocapensis* by Wesołowska (2024). This species is likely a synonym and the unknown male of *H. capensis* (Wesołowska, 1986), as they were collected from the same locality at the same time.

Figs 1–3. *Heliocapensis bellus*. 1–2. Male. 3. Male palp. Photo: 1–2. Peter Webb. 3. Wesołowska (1986).

Heliocapensis capensis (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Cape Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1986 from Sneeuwberg near Clanwilliam. The species has been sampled from areas around Cape Town and Clanwilliam, as well as from the Northern Cape (EOO=28 040 km²; AOO=32 km²; 7–719 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Clanwilliam, Sneeuwberg (-32.16, 18.89); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.98, 18.43); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38). **Northern Cape:** Nieuwoudtville (-31.37, 19.11); Tankwa Karoo National Park (-32.28, 19.82).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers, sampled from the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from wide range, with no known threats. It is protected in the Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024), Fernkloof Nature Reserve (Hamilton-Atwell & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023) and Tankwa Karoo National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Wesołowska, 1986). Now placed in *Heliocapensis* (Wesołowska 2024).

Figs 1–4. *Heliocapensis capensis*. 1–2. Female. 3–4. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2. Peter Webb. 3–4. From Wesołowska (1986).

Heliocapensis charlesi (Wesołowska, 2003)

COMMON NAME: Charles' Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2003 from Prieska in the Northern Cape. The species has a wide distribution and is known from seven provinces (EOO=433 271 km²; AOO=68 km²; 459–1809 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62); Luckhoff district, Bankfontein farm (-29.73, 24.77). **Gauteng:** IreneEzemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.70, 28.94); , Gem Village field (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Rietvleidam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Newcastle district, Normandien farms (-27.55, 29.49); Newcastle district, Moorfield farm (-27.52, 29.43). **Mpumalanga:** Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Machadodorp (-25.66, 30.26). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Oryx Game farm (-28.42, 22.17); Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska, Remhoogte farm (-29.52, 23.00); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Kathu district, Farm Pniel (-28.58, 24.52). **Western Cape:** 40 km NE Ceres on Touwsriver road (-33.36, 19.31).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Thicket and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). The species was also sampled from agro-ecosystems such as lucerne pine plantations and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. It is protected in seven protected areas, including Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018), Golden Gate Highlands National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024) and Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska, 2003). Now placed in *Heliocapensis* (Wesołowska 2024).

Figs 1–10. *Heliocapensis charlesi*. 1–2, 4. Female. 3, 5. Male. 6–8. Male palp. 9, 10. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2. Ruan Booysen. 3, 6, 9. From Wesołowska (2003). 4, 5, 7, 8, 10. Charles Haddad.

Heliocapensis claviger (Simon, 1901)

COMMON NAME: Four-Spotted Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described in 1901 from the Western Cape, with the type locality only as Cape Colony from a unspecified site. The species is presently known from two countries (EOO=307 659 km²; AOO=56 km²; 4–125 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Mozambique.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Fernkloof Nature Reserve, Hermanus District (-34.47, 19.27); Goukamma Nature Reserve (-34.03, 22.55); Kalk Bay (-34.19, 18.42); Kommetjie (-34.16, 18.34); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Simon's Town (-34.19, 18.42); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38); Yzerfontein (-33.34, 18.16).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living spider moving around on vegetation. In KwaZulu-Natal, several immature specimens were collected from *Vachellia xanthophloea* bark (Haddad, 2016). The species was sampled from leaf litter and low-growing foliage in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. It is protected in more than six protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Both sexes were described by Simon (1901). Additional data was added by Wesolowska (1986) and Wesolowska & Haddad (2009). Now placed in *Heliocapensis* (Wesolowska 2024).

Heliocapensis claviger
(Simon, 1901)

Figs 1–10. *Heliocapensis claviger*. 1–4. Male. 5, 6. Male habitus. 7. Epigyne. 8–10. Male palp. Credits: 1–2. Vida van der Walt. 3–4. Peter Webb. 5, 7, 8. From Wesolowska (1986). 6, 9, 10. Charles Haddad.

Heliocapensis deserticola (Simon, 1901)

COMMON NAME: Desert Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1901 from de Aar in the Northern Cape. The species is presently known only from a few localities in three provinces (EOO=386 583 km²; AOO=24 km²; 881–1999 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cradock (-32.16, 25.61); Hogsback, Amatola Forestry Company (-32.57, 26.94). **Mpumalanga:** Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.42, 30.10); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.10). **Northern Cape:** De Aar (-30.64, 24.01); Goegap Nature Reserve (-29.66, 17.99); Nababeep district, Jakkalswater Guest Farm (-29.15, 17.48); Namaqua National Park, Near Skilpad Rest Camp (-30.16, 17.76).

LIFESTYLE: A ground- and plant-dwelling species recorded from the Succulent Karoo and Grassland biomes (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There is no known threats and it is protected in the Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve and Goegap Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Simon (1901) and the female was added by Wesolowska (1986). Listed in *Heliocapensis* by Wesolowska (2024).

Figs 1–7. *Heliocapensis deserticola*. 1–2. Immature female from Jakkalsdraai. 3. Female from Dullstroom. 4. Female. 5. Male palp. 6, 7. Epigyne. Credits: 1–3. Peter Webb. 4, 6. Charles Haddad. 5, 7. From Wesolowska (1986).

Heliocapensis maluti (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2014)

COMMON NAME: Maluti Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species widespread in central and southern Lesotho that was described in 2014, but it was also recently recorded from South Africa. The species has a wide distribution range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Namaqua National Park, Koeroebees (-30.14, 17.70).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dweller collected from under rocks.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threats to the species; it is protected in the Namaqua National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2014) described from Lesotho. Recently recorded for the first time from South Africa (Haddad & Wesołowska, 2024).

Figs 1–4. *Heliocapensis maluti*. 1, 2. Male. 3. Male palp. 4. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3, 4. Wesołowska & Haddad (2014).

Heliocapensis mirabilis (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Sneeuberg *Heliocapensis* Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1986 from Sneeuberg near Clanwilliam. It is known from two provinces (EOO=<1000 km²; AOO=24 km²; 78–103 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Richtersveld National Park, Halfmens Pass (-28.12, 16.96); Richtersveld National Park, near Akkedis Pass (-28.13, 16.98); Richtersveld National Park, Near Hand of God (-28.09, 16.97); Richtersveld National Park, Sendelingsdrif Camp (-28.12, 16.89). **Western Cape:** Algeria Forest Station, 41 km SSE of Clanwilliam (-32.18, 18.88); Clanwilliam, Sneeuberg (-32.16, 18.89); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: Plant-dweller sampled from Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats. The species receives protection in the Richtersveld National Park (Haddad & Wesołowska, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Male was described by Wesołowska (1986) and additional data was provided by Haddad & Wesołowska (2013). The female was described by Haddad & Wesołowska (2024).

Figs 1–8. *Heliocapensis mirabilis*. 1–3. Female. 4. Male. 5, 6. Male palp. 7, 8. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3–7. Charles Haddad. 8. Haddad & Wesołowska (2024).

Heliocapensis peckhami (Simon, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Peckham's *Heliocapensis* Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1902, with the type locality given only as Cape Colony. The species is sampled from different localities in the Western Cape (EOO=2 645 km²; AOO=20 km²; 7–78 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<5 000 km²), some more sampling is needed to determine its range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63); Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Clanwilliam, Sneeuberg (-32.16, 18.89); Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Presently protected in the Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Simon (1902) described the male and Wesolowska (1986) the female.

Figs 1–6. *Heliocapensis peckhami*. 1–3. Female. 4. Abdomen. 5. Male palp. 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Peter Webb. 3, 4. From Wesolowska (2024). 5, 6. From Wesolowska (1986).

Heliocapensis portentosus (Wesołowska, 1986)

COMMON NAME: Tulbagh Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1986 and presently known only from the type locality, Tulbagh in the Western Cape (EEO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 160 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine its range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Tulbagh (-33.28, 19.14).

LIFESTYLE: Plant-dweller sampled on plants from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is very poorly known. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male. Now listed in *Heliocapensis* (Wesołowska 2024).

Fig. 1. *Heliocapensis portentosus*. Male palp. From Wesołowska (1986)

Heliocapensis redimitus (Simon, 1910)

COMMON NAME: Kamaggas Heliocapensis Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 1910 and known from only the female. The type locality is Kamaggas (EOO=400 km^2; AOO=8 km^2; 230 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine its range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Goegap Nature Reserve (-29.68, 17.95); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.40).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living plant-dweller sampled the Succulent Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine its range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesolowska (1986). Now placed in *Heliocapensis* (Wesolowska 2024).

Figs 1–3. *Heliocapensis redimitus*. 1. Female. 2, 3. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2024). 3. From Wesolowska (1986).

Heliocapensis termitophagus (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2002)

COMMON NAME: Termite-feeding *Heliocapensis* Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic species described in 2002 from Bloemfontein. The species has been sampled from two provinces, including three protected areas (EOO=23 005 km²; AOO= 20 km²; 1235-1399 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide, geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.30, 24.81). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein district, Deelhoek farm (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: It has a wide geographical range and is protected in the Benfontein Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2023), Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve and Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2002), with a junior synonym (*Heliocapensis thaleri* (Wesołowska, 2009)). Transferred to *Heliocapensis* by Wesołowska (2024).

Figs 1–7. *Heliocapensis termitophagus*. 1–3. Female. 4. Male habitus. 5. Epigynes. 6. Male palp. 7. Male palpal femur. Credits: 1. Ruan Booysen. 2, 3. Vida van der Walt. 4–7. From Wesołowska & Haddad (2002).

GENUS *HELIOPHANUS* C.L. Koch, 1833

The genus *Heliophanus* C.L. Koch, 1833 is known from 91 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Nine species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Heliophanus sunny jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Heliophanus cupreus* (Walckenaer, 1802)

MORPHOLOGY: Small or medium sized spiders, ranging 2.5–6 mm, the colouration is usually black, sometimes with a metallic shine. On the abdomen of many species there are two pairs of round white spots, sometimes also with light front margin. In some species, the abdomen is differently coloured: *H. gramineus* is creamy-grey with transverse brown spots, *H. deformis* has typical spots, but on a reddish fawn background. The males of *Heliophanus* are characterized by the presence of a large apophysis on the ventral surface of the palpal femur. Some species have a sclerotized rim on the ventral surface of the femur on the pro-lateral side. Most species have an epigyne with a single large central depression.

DISTRIBUTION: Members of *Heliophanus* s. str. are widely distributed in Palaearctic, Oriental and Afrotropical Regions.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living spiders found on ground or plant-dwellers collected from a wide variety of habitats.

TAXONOMY: The African species were last revised by Wesolowska (1986). Several species have been added since.

Figs 1–2. *Heliophanus gramineus*. 1. Male. 2. Female. Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Figs 3–4. *Heliophanus*: General appearance of male and female. After Wesolowska (2024).

Heliophanus africanus Wesolowska, 1986

COMMON NAME: Gauteng Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Gauteng endemic species described in 1986 from the Melville Koppies. The species is undersampled and presently known only from two localities in Gauteng (EOO=<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 144–1719 m a.s.l.). Due to the small range, the status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Melville Koppies (-26.17, 27.99); Irene, Gem Village field (-25.89, 28.23).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female ((Wesolowska, 1986)).

Figs 1–3. *Heliophanus africanus*. 1, 2. Female. 3. Epigyne. Credits 1, 2. Peter Webb. 3. From Wesolowska (1986).

Heliophanus deformis Wesolowska, 1986

COMMON NAME: Rusty Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described in 1986 from Angola. In South Africa, the species is only known from the Northern Cape (EOO=<1000 km²; AOO=16 km²). Due to the large distribution range, the species is of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Namaqua National Park, Skilpad (-30.16, 17.71); Richtersveld National Park, Halfmens Pass (-28.12, 16.96); Richtersveld National Park, SE of Akkedis Pass (-28.18, 17.04); Richtersveld National Park, near Akkedis Pass (-28.13, 16.99).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers. Sampled by beating karooid bushes and trees.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threats. The species is protected in the Namaqua and Richtersveld National Parks.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: A species that was previously known from Angola (Wesolowska 1986); reported from South Africa for the first time by Haddad & Wesolowska (2024).

Figs 1–9. *Heliophanus deformis*. 1–3. Male. 4. Female. 5, 6. Epigyne. 7–9. Male palp. 10. Male palpal femur. Credits 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3–9. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2024).

Heliophanus designatus (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)

COMMON NAME: Willowmore Heliophanus Sunny Jumping spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic species described in 1903 as *Sittacus designatus* from Willowmore. The species is undersampled and presently known only from the type locality (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 144–1719 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Willowmore (-33.30, 23.50).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living spiders found on ground or plants.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Peckham & Peckham, 1903). The species was transferred to *Heliophanus* by Maddison *et al.* (2020).

Fig. 1. *Heliophanus designatus* female abdomen. From Peckham & Peckham (1903).

Heliophanus gramineus Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Mottled Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2013 from Hogsback in the Eastern Cape. The species has been sampled from four provinces (EOO=218 195 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 120–1498 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park, Woody Cape (-33.75, 26.38); Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve (-32.70, 26.52); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.93); Katberg State Forest (-32.47, 26.67); Mount Coke State Forest (-32.99, 27.48); Glen Gariff, Gleneden Lagoon Mouth (-32.88, 28.09). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick district, Wakefield farm (-29.47, 29.89). **Limpopo:** Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.32). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

LIFESTYLE: The known specimens were all collected by beating vegetation, litter sifting and hand collecting, especially at the bases of grasses. Sampled from the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats and the species is protected in five protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The female was described by Wesolowska and Haddad (2013) and the male by Wesolowska and Haddad (2018).

Figs 1–9. *Heliophanus gramineus*. 1–3. Male. 4–6. Female. 7. Epigyne. 8. Male palpal femur. 9. Male palp. Credits: 1–6. Vida van der Walt. 7. From Wesolowska and Haddad (2013). 8, 9. From Wesolowska and Haddad (2018).

Heliophanus hamifer Simon, 1886

COMMON NAME: Mozambican Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1886 from Mozambique. The species is presently known from six countries. In South Africa, it is only known from the Limpopo Province (EEO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 857 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Madagascar, Comoros, Seychelles, South Africa. Introduced to Brazil (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Balloon Forest (-24.19, 30.33).

LIFESTYLE: The known specimens were all collected by beating vegetation, litter sifting and hand collecting in the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Simon (1886). It was revised and the female described by Wesołowska (1986).

Figs 1–6. *Heliophanus hamifer*. 1, 2. Female. 3. Male habitus. 4. Male palp. 5. Male palpal femur. 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Peter Webb. 3–6. From Wesołowska (1986).

Heliophanus horrifera Wesolowska, 1986

COMMON NAME: Cape Town Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1986 from Cape Town. The species is presently known only from Cape Town and Stellenbosch (EOO=<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 7–103 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85).

LIFESTYLE: The species were sampled from vegetation in the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from the female.

Figs 1–3. *Heliophanus horrifera*. 1, 2. Female. 3. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 3. From Wesolowska (1986).

Heliophanus pratti Peckham & Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Pratt's Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1903 from Willowmore. The species was also collected in Namibia. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces (EOO=252 693 km²; AOO=40 km²; 3–1415 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Willowmore (-33.30, 23.50). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Cape Town, Princess Valley (-33.90, 18.38); Constantia, Bergvliet Flats (-34.01, 18.44); Jacobsbaai (-33.15, 18.03); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Table Mountain National Park, Devils Peak (-33.92, 18.45); Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38); West Coast National Park (-33.23, 18.12); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.35, 20.49).

LIFESTYLE: A plant-dweller sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Succulent Karoo and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in five protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Peckham & Peckham (1903), with Wesołowska (1986) adding additional data and drawings. The female is unknown.

Figs 1–2. *Heliophanus pratti*. 1. Male palp. 2. Male palpal femur. From Wesołowska (2006).

Heliophanus pygmaeus Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000

COMMON NAME: Pygmy Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Tanzania in 2000. The species is known from five African countries. In South Africa, it has been found in three provinces (EOO=73 710 km²; AOO=28 km²; 91–904 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Limpopo:* Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.41, 26.75). *Mpumalanga:* Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Kambeni (-25.15, 31.27); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Numbi (-25.14, 31.20); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Shabeni (-25.10, 31.23); Kruger National Park, Satara (-24.43, 31.85); Kruger National Park, Satara (-24.38, 31.78).

LIFESTYLE: Quick-moving, tiny, beetle-like spider sampled from vegetation and grass tussocks. They have been sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in four protected areas, Atherstone Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park, Ndumo Game Reserve and Tembe Elephant Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: *Heliophanus pygmaeus* was described Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2000) from a male from Tanzania, with additional notes added by Wesolowska (2004) and Wesolowska & Cumming (2008).

Figs 1–6. *Heliophanus pygmaeus*. 1. Male. 2, 3. Male palp. 4. Male palpal femur. 5. Female abdomen. 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Charles Haddad. 3–6. After Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2000).

Heliophanus sororius Wesolowska, 2003

COMMON NAME: Golden Gate Heliophanus Sunny Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described in 2003 from Golden Gate Highlands National Park in the Free State. The species was also sampled from Lesotho. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces (EOO=25 394 km²; AOO=16 km²; 1328–2398 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Hogsback (-32.56, 26.91). *Free State:* Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.62). *Mpumalanga:* Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

LIFESTYLE: Plant-dweller sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. Protected in the Golden Gate Highlands National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Male was described by Wesolowska (2003) and the female by Wesolowska and Haddad (2018).

Figs 1–7. *Heliophanus sororius*. 1. Male. 2–4. Male palp. 5. Male palpal femur. 6, 7. Epigyne. Credits: 1–3, 6. Charles Haddad. 4, 5, 7. From Wesolowska & Haddad (2018).

GENUS *HISPO* Simon, 1886

The genus includes nine species, but only one is known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

COMMON NAME: Hispo jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hispo cingulata* Simon, 1886

MORPHOLOGY: Small to large spiders ranging from about 3.5 to 8 mm long. Sexual dimorphism is not marked. Carapace: moderately high, somewhat flattened; constricted behind posterior median eyes and usually with two shallow depressions behind anterior medians; fovea present or absent; microsculpturing variable, cuticle sometimes iridescent; eyes: anterior eyes contiguous, apices level or slightly procurved; posterior median eyes relatively small, closer to anterior laterals than to posterior laterals; posterior row usually narrower than anterior row, with a space between the posterior lateral eyes and the lateral margins of the carapace. Abdomen: elongate. Legs: moderately long and slender, I and sometimes II enlarged or elongate; fringes usually lacking, spines weak to moderately strong, usually more numerous on posterior legs.

LIFESTYLE: Ant-like in appearance, especially when immature. They forage under bark and in leaf litter, moving in the same way as ants. They construct thin silk retreats attached to the inner surface of a flake of bark or inside a narrow crack on a tree trunk (Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008).

TAXONOMY: *Hispo* is closely related to the genus *Massagris*. The single species, *Hispo georgius* (Peckham & Peckham, 1892), was redescribed by Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008).

Figs 1–2. *Hispo georgius* male. Credit: Vida van der Walt.

Hispo georgius (Peckham & Peckham, 1892)

COMMON NAME: Hispo Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1892 from Madagascar as *Leptorchestes georgius*. It has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known from five provinces (EOO=1 646 737 km²; AOO=32 km²; 47–1307 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, D.R. Congo, Kenya, Madagascar, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Settlers (-24.95, 28.52). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Mopani–Mooiplaas (-23.56, 31.45); Kruger National Park, Mopani–Tsendze (-23.69, 31.51); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Kambeni (-25.15, 31.27). **Western Cape:** Plettenberg Bay (-34.06, 23.36).

LIFESTYLE: They were sampled from under the bark of large trees such as *Vachellia*, *Commiphora* and *Bauhinia* in the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011). Their retreats are constructed of thin silk stuck onto the inner surface of a flake of bark or inside a narrow crack on a tree trunk.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in four protected areas: Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010) and Kruger National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Redescribed by Wesołowska & Cumming (2008).

Figs 1–9. *Hispo georgius*. 1–4. Male. 5. Female. 7–8. Male palp. 9. Epigyne. Credits: 1. Ruan Booysen. 2, 7, 8. Charles Haddad. 3, 6, 9. From: Wesołowska & Cumming (2008). 4. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 5. After Wanless (1985).

GENUS *HOLCOLAETIS* Simon, 1886

The genus *Holcolaetis* is represented by seven species, of which two are recorded in South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

COMMON NAME: Holcolaetis jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Holcolaetis xerampelina* Simon, 1886

MORPHOLOGY: Flattened hairy spiders; medium to large (8–16 mm); sexes morphologically similar but sexually dimorphic in colour, except males usually have longer, more slender legs; colour patterns similar inter-specifically. Carapace low, longer than broad, widest at about level of coxae II–III, with transverse depression between posterior lateral eyes and fovea; eyes: anterior eyes closely set, equally or subequally spaced, with apices procurved in frontal view; anterior laterals equal to or greater than half the diameter of anterior medians; posterior medians relatively large, closer to and just outside optical axis of anterior laterals; posterior laterals more or less as large as anterior laterals. Abdomen characteristically marked with a broad dorsal dentate band. Legs are moderately long and robust, with stronger build in females; the anteriors often feature strong fringes; claws are smooth or pectinate; scopulae are absent; tufts are present.

LIFESTYLE: They are known from different habitats. The species have been sighted on tree trunks but also from walls.

TAXONOMY: The African species were revised by Wanless (1985).

Figs 1–2. *Holcolaetis* species. 1. *H. zuluensis* female. 2. *H. vellerea* male. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Vida van der Walt.

Holcolaetis vellerea Simon, 1910

COMMON NAME: Holcolaetis Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1910 from São Tomé. Distributed throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known from two provinces (EEO=9881 km²; AOO=24 km²; 1119–1412 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Cameroon, D.R. Congo, Equatorial Guinea (São Tomé), Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mozambique, Rwanda, South Africa, Uganda, Yemen and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Acacia Lodge Game Reserve (-24.56, 27.37); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Rooiberg (-24.77, 27.73). **Gauteng:** Kameeldrift (-25.66, 28.32); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane, Garsfontein (-25.79, 28.30); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19).

LIFESTYLE: They are known from different habitats. The species has been sighted on tree trunks but also from walls, where they live among loose bricks or rubble. The species was sampled from the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected at the Acacia Lodge Game Reserve and Pretoria National Botanical Garden (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesolowska & Cumming (2008).

Figs 1–6. *Holcolaetis vellerea* 1, 2. Male. 3, 4. Female. 5. Male palp. 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3. After Wanless (1985). 4. Peter Webb. 5, 6. From: Wesolowska and Cumming (2008).

Holcolaetis zuluensis Lawrence, 1937

COMMON NAME: Zululand Holcolaetis Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1937 from Kosi Bay Nature Reserve in South Africa. The species is also known from Tanzania and Mozambique. In South Africa, it is known from four provinces (EOO=376 433 km²; AOO=96 km²; 4–1427 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Tanzania and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-28.36, 32.42); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie's Island (-28.10, 32.45); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-29.29, 26.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Otobotini (-27.42, 32.10); Pietermaritzburg (-29.36, 30.23); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park, Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Western Soutpansberg, Little Leigh farm (-22.95, 29.87); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Alldays district, Rochdale farm (-22.54, 29.41). **Mpumalanga:** Komatipoort, Sommerreg farm (-25.53, 31.82); Kruger National Park, Malelane Gate (-25.45, 31.54); Malelane (-25.49, 31.50).

LIFESTYLE: The species is frequently associated with bark. In Ndumo Game Reserve, it was sampled from the fever tree bark (Haddad, 2016). Both sexes have flattened bodies that enable them to crawl into narrow crevices and under bark. Egg sacs are constructed under bark either on the inner bark surface or on the tree trunk. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it has been recorded from eight protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The female was described by Lawrence (1937) and additional information was added by Wesolowska & Haddad (2009).

Figs 1–7. *Holcolaetis zuluensis*. 1, 2. Female. 3, 4. Male. 5, 6. Epigyne. 7. Male palp. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2, 3. Vida van der Walt. 4. Charles Haddad. 5. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 6, 7. From: Wesolowska & Haddad (2009).

GENUS *HOMALATTUS* White, 1841

The genus *Homalattus* is represented by six species, with three species known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

COMMON NAME: Homalattus jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Homalattus pustulatus* (White, 1841)

MORPHOLOGY: Total length 3–5 mm. Carapace flat, transverse, not as wide as the body, covered with papillae; eyes located on short elevations of the thorax; eyes arranged in three rows, with the front row comprising four eyes placed on the front margin of the carapace at nearly equal distances from each other; the two intermediate eyes are the largest. Abdomen flat and compressed, as broad as long; somewhat convex above in front, straight; somewhat pointed behind, with rounded sides. Legs 4123, first pair stoutest; tibia I longer than patella, armed, metatarsus I longer than the tarsus

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dweller.

TAXONOMY: Genus not revised.

Figs 1–4. *Homalattus* spp. 1–3. Habitus. 4. *Homalattus punctatus*. Credits: 1–3. From White (1841). 4. From Peckham & Peckham (1903).

***Homalattus coriaceus* Simon, 1902**

COMMON NAME: Homalattus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described in 1902 with type series from Sierra Leone and South Africa (EOO in SA = <math><100\text{ km}^2</math>; AOO=4 km²; 7 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range in Africa, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Sierra Leone, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Homalattus obscurus Peckham & Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Homalattus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described in 1903 with types from Mpumalanga (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 7 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Due to small geographic range listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.10, 30.78).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dweller.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Fig. 1. Epigyne. From Peckham & Peckham (1903).

Homalattus punctatus Peckham & Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Spotted Homalattus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic species described from Durban in 1903. Sampled from only two other localities near Durban (EOO=138 km²; AOO=12 km²; 17–496 m a.s.l.). This species is undersampled and more sampling is needed to do an assessment. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Savanna and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from a female.

Figs 1–4. *Homalattus punctatus* 1, 2. Female. 3. Female abdomen. 4. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3, 4. From Peckham & Peckham (1903).

GENUS *HYLLUS* C.L. Koch, 1846

The genus *Hyllus* is represented by 75 species and subspecies, of which six are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

COMMON NAME: Hyllus jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hyllus giganteus* C.L. Koch, 1846

MORPHOLOGY: They are sturdy, solid-looking, large spiders. They are stout, hairy and often dull in colour. The carapace is broad and oval, slightly longer than broad, with a somewhat truncated rear edge. The carapace is fairly high, featuring a long, sloping thorax and steep sides. The cephalic region is relatively short and slightly convex. Abdomen oval, rounded at the front and tapered to a truncate rear, often with intricate markings. Legs are long and stout, with legs I the longest; front legs on some segments are covered with dense fringes of thin, black hair. The colour and pattern of other species varies.

LIFESTYLE: Species are typically found in silken cells within low vegetation in open areas. They forage on shrubs and grasses.

TAXONOMY: Six species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

Figs 1–2. *Hyllus argyrotoxus* female. Credits: Peter Webb.

Figs 3–4. *Hyllus brevitarsis* female. Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Figs 5–6. *Hyllus dotatus* female. Credits: Peter Webb.

Hyllus argyrotoxa Simon, 1902

COMMON NAME: Black And White Hyllus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Simon (1902) from South Africa, with the type locality given only as Zululand. The species is recorded from several African countries from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. It has a wide distribution throughout South Africa and presently known from seven provinces (EOO=1913 700 km²; AOO=324 km²; 17–1558 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Eswatini, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Cintsa (-32.83, 28.06); East London, Gonubie (-32.94, 28.03); East London, Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90); Great Fish River Wetland Park (-33.48, 27.13); Keurkloof district, Ferndale farm (-33.68, 24.83). **Gauteng:** Buffelsdrift, Wonderboom (-25.37, 28.22); Enkeldoorn (-25.38, 28.70); Pretoria/Tshwane, National Botanical Gardens (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Rosslyn Akasia (-25.622, 28.086); Tswaing Nature Reserve (-25.41, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Reserve (-28.40, 32.18); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Howick district, Wakefield farm (-29.47, 29.89); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.70); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.60, 32.02); Mlawula Nature Reserve (-26.22, 32.00); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Mpushini (-29.62, 30.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Pongola district, Vergeval farm Ngotsche (-28.92, 31.35); 15 km N Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); St Michael's on Sea (-30.82, 30.38); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96). **Limpopo:** Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.14, 29.92); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Ebeneazer Dam (-23.94, 29.98); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Kampersrus district, Madrid farm (-24.48, 30.90); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park, Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Koedoesvlei, Western Soutpansberg (-23.06, 29.49); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Limpopo Valley Reserve, Venetia (-22.32, 29.32); Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg (-22.94, 29.87); Mara Research Station (-23.13, 29.54);

Figs 1–5. *Hyllus argyrotoxa*. 1, 2. Male. 3–5. Female. Credits: 1, 3. Peter Webb. 2, 4. From Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2000). 5. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Hyllus argyrotoxus (continued)

Mogalakwena Nature Reserve, Canterbury farm (-22.73, 28.77); Mogalakwena Nature Reserve, Huilbosch farm (-22.72, 28.81); Mogalakwena Nature Reserve, Nooitgedacht farm (-22.76, 28.70); Mphadhuli Cycad Reserve (-22.42, 30.49); Ndengeza (-23.31, 30.41); Nwanedi Game Reserve (-22.64, 30.37); Pafuri, Waller's Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Soutpansberg, Stoke farm (-22.48, 29.88); Tshulu Camp Venda (-22.580, 30.809). **Mpumalanga:** Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park, Lwakahle (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park, Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park, Letaba (-23.83, 31.58); Kruger National Park, Mopani–Tsendze (-23.55, 31.44); Kruger National Park, Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-24.98, 31.59); Kruger National Park, Vutome (-25.24, 32.08); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit district, Brondal farm (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit district, Glenwood farm (-29.87, 30.98); Nelspruit district, Hall and Sons farm (-25.43, 31.01). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Buffelsfontein farm Rustenburg (-25.57, 27.17); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Doring Bay (-31.81, 18.24).

LIFESTYLE: This species was mainly collected from shrubs and trees. It is a highly mobile travelling species, moving boldly through low plants. One female was collected from a retreat with an egg sac constructed on the underside of a leaf. Silk was used to fold the leaf, forming a broad tube in which the egg sac was constructed. The species was sampled in South Africa from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Forest, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes. The species was also found in agroecosystems such as avocado, citrus, cotton and macadamia (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesolowska and Russell-Smith (2000).

Figs 1–9. *Hyllus argyrotoxus*. 1–3. Male. 4–6. Female. 7. Male palp. 8, 9. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3, 6. Charles Haddad. 4, 5. Peter Webb. 7, 8. From Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2000). 9. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Hyllus brevitarsis Simon, 1902

COMMON NAME: Brown Hyllus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Simon (1902), with the type locality given only as Cape of Good Hope. Recorded from several African countries. From South Africa, it has been recorded from six provinces (EOO=612 855 km²; AOO=176 km²; 7–1303 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Mozambique, Namibia, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); East London, Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Mount Coke State Forest (-32.99, 27.47); Mbashee River Mouth (-32.83, 28.92); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW Cape St Francis (-34.20, 24.70). **Gauteng:** Dinokeng, Baviaanspoort (-25.67, 28.37); Enkeldoorn (-25.38, 28.70); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Greytown (-29.05, 30.60); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Mpushini (-29.62, 30.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngotshe district, Vergeval farm (-27.35, 31.61); 15 km N Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Alldays district, Rochdale farm (-22.54, 29.41); Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.41, 26.75); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Koedoesvlei, Western Soutpansberg (-23.06, 29.49); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg (-22.94, 29.87); Mogalakwena Nature Reserve, Nooitgedacht farm (-22.76, 28.70); Mogalakwena Nature Reserve, Huilbosch farm (-22.72, 28.81); Mphadhuli Cycad Reserve (-22.42, 30.49); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Nylstroom/Modimolle (-24.69, 28.40); Steenbokpan (-23.71, 27.27). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-24.98, 31.59); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit district, Brondal farm (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit district, Glenwood farm (-29.87, 30.98).

Figs 1–4. *Hyllus brevitarsis*. 1, 2. Male. 3, 4. Subadult female. Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Hyllus brevitarsis (continued)

LIFESTYLE: This medium-sized *Hyllus* sp. was occasionally collected by beating foliage of shrubs and trees in various savannah and floodplain habitats. Some specimens were extracted from retreats constructed on the ventral side of leaves of *Sansevieria hyacinthoides* plants. One female was extracted from a silk retreat constructed in a grass inflorescence. This species was only collected in late spring and summer. The spider sat still and adpressed to the substrate, and resembled a honey bee, both in size and in its striped orange/black abdomen (Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008).

In South Africa, it has been sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Forest, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled from avocado, lemon and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesołowska (2008).

Figs 1–8. *Hyllus brevitarsis*. 1–4. Female. 5. Female, abdominal variations. 6, 7. Epigyne. 8. Male palp. Credits: 1, 2. Peter Webb. 3. Vida van der Walt. 4. Charles Haddad. 5, 6, 8. From Wesołowska (2008). 7. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Hyllus dotatus (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)

COMMON NAME: Dotatus Hyllus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1903 as *Habrocestum dotatum* from Mashonaland, Zimbabwe. The species has a wide distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa, it is known from all nine provinces (EOO=998 034 km²; AOO=220 km²; 1–1732 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, D.R. Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Yemen, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); Grahamstown (-32.24, 24.53); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.61, 26.41); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Irene, Gem Village field (-25.89, 28.23); Rietondale Research Station (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatsdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-28.36, 32.42); Entendweni (-28.33, 31.08); Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Ifafa Beach (-30.45, 30.64); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (-29.29, 26.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.39, 29.67); Makatini Flats (-27.25, 32.22); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Midlands, Richmond, Maybole Plantation (-29.76, 30.25); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 33.91); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 32.24); Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.41, 26.75); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Kruger National Park, Orpen Rest camp (-24.47, 31.39); Kruger National Park, Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Lekgalameetse, farm The Downs (-24.14, 30.31); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (24.65, 28.67); Vhembe Biosphere, Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.02, 29.10); Vhembe Biosphere, Gondeni communal land (-22.90, 29.99); Vhembe Biosphere, Mara Research Station (-23.04, 29.66); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95). **Mpumalanga:** Crocodile River Gorge, 20 km East of Nelspruit (-25.32, 31.13); Kruger National Park, Mopani–Dzombo (-23.45, 31.38); Kruger National Park, Mopani–Mooiplaas (-23.58, 31.46); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Kambeni (-25.15, 31.27); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Numbi (-25.15, 31.19); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop–Shabeni (-25.15, 31.20);

Figs 1–10. *Hyllus dotatus*. 1–3. Female. 4, 5. Male. 6–8. Epigyne. 9, 10. Male palp. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2, 4, 6, 9. From Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2000). 3, 5, 7, 8, 10. Charles Haddad.

Hyllus dotatus (continued)

Kruger National Park, Satara (-24.38, 31.78); Kruger National Park, Satara-N'wanetsi (-24.44, 31.88); Nelspruit (-25.34, 31.77). **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Brits (-25.62, 27.77). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.57, 24.20); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Fisherhaven (-34.47, 19.27).

LIFESTYLE: A free-living plant-dweller found on the foliage of shrubs and trees in various savannah and floodplain habitats. It was also sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Forest, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes, as well as from agroecosystems such as cotton, kenaf and maize (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: See Wesolowska and Russell-Smith (2000) for description of both sexes.

Figs 1–5. *Hyllus dotatus*. 1–3. Female. 4, 5. Male. Credits: 1–3. Peter Webb. 4, 5. Vida van der Walt.

Hyllus flavescens Simon, 1902

COMMON NAME: Natal Hyllus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 1902, with the type locality only given as Natal. The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: type locality only Natal.

LIFESTYLE: Unknown.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the species and to determine its range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Simon, 1902). Never redescribed or illustrated.

Hyllus treleaveni Peckham & Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Treleaven's Hyllus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1902 from Zimbabwe. The species has been recorded throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known from seven provinces (EOO=766 371 km²; AOO=180 km²; 10–1558 m a.s.l.) Due to the wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, D.R. Congo, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90). **Free State:** Vaal Dam (-26.90, 28.12). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest (-28.30, 32.36); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Entendweni (-28.20, 32.15); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Mlawula Nature Reserve (-26.22, 32.00); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngotshe district, Vergeval farm (-27.35, 31.61); Phinda Resource Reserve (-26.87, 32.27); Pongola Nature Reserve (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Ellisras/Lephalale (-23.67, 27.71); Goro Game Reserve (-22.99, 29.43); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Hoedspruit, Vienna Game Farm (-24.30, 30.97); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park, near Skukuza (-22.93, 31.02); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Balloon farm (-24.17, 30.25); Leopard Creek Reserve, Caledonia farm (-23.83, 27.95); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg (-22.94, 29.87); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.70); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Nylstroom/Modimolle (-24.69, 28.40); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Orpen Camp (-24.47, 31.40); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47); Trichardsdal (-24.16, 30.39); Tshulu Camp Venda (-22.58, 30.81); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Warmbaths Dam (-24.87, 28.26). **Mpumalanga:** Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Franklin Park, near Kampersrus (-24.55, 30.94); Komatipoort, Sommerreg farm (-25.53, 31.82); Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-25.00, 31.97); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Marloth Park (-25.35, 31.78). **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Swartruggens (-25.64, 26.70). **Western Cape:** Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25).

Figs 1–5. *Hyllus treleaveni*. 1–2. Female. 3. Female abdomens, showing variation in patterns. 4. Face of female. 5. Epigyne. Credits 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3–5. From Wesotowska & Cumming (2004).

Hyllus treleaveni (continued)

LIFESTYLE: This species is Africa's largest jumping spider and was commonly collected from foliage, such as broadleaved shrubs in various savannah and floodplain habitats. It has been recorded from Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Forest, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known from a wide range, with no known threats. In South Africa, it has been sampled from >10 protected area.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesolowska and Cumming (2004).

Figs 1–7. *Hyllus treleaveni*. 1, 2, 5. Male. 3. Male and female during courtship. 4. Female with grasshopper prey. 6. Male palp. 7. Epigynes. Credits 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3, 4. Charles Haddad. 5–7. From Wesolowska & Cumming (2004).

GENUS *ICIUS* Simon, 1876

A moderately large genus with 49 species, with 10 recorded from the Afrotropical Region (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

COMMON NAME: *Icius* jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Icius hamatus* (C.L. Koch, 1846)

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace oval, chelicerae long, unidentate, with a sizable additional tooth at the base. Sternum blackish. Abdomen ovoid, in some species with broad white band, stripe or spots; dorsum with sparse long dark bristles. Legs with long spines and covered in thin, long, black hairs. The males have long chelicerae, a palp with a single tibial apophysis (sometimes bifid), an elongate bulb with a posterior lobe, and a short embolus. The females have an epigyne with straight seminal ducts and rounded receptacles.

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling species that was mainly sampled by hand from rocks, bases of grass tussocks, and the soil surface.

TAXONOMY: The African species have not yet been revised.

Figs 1–4. *Icius insolidus*. 1, 2 Female. 3, 4. Male. 1, 3. Dorsal view. 2, 4. Anterior view.
Credits: Vida van der Walt.

Icius dendryphantoides Strand, 1909

COMMON NAME: Simonstown Icius Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 1909 and known only from the type locality, Simon's Town (EEO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Simon's Town (-34.19, 18.43).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female (Strand, 1909).

Fig. 1. *Icius dendryphantoides*, epigyne. From Prószyński (1987)

Icius desertorum Simon, 1901

COMMON NAME: Matjiesfontein Icius Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic species described in 1901 and known only from the type locality, Matjiesfontein (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 912 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Matjiesfontein (-33.25, 20.67).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from a female (Simon, 1901b).

Icius insolidus (Wesołowska, 1999)

COMMON NAME: Common Icius Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1999 as *Menemerus insolidus* from Kimberley in the Northern Cape. Known from three African countries and recorded from eight South African provinces (EOO=672 509 km²; AOO=132 km²; 37–1762 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein district, Deelhoek farm (-28.83, 26.08); Bloemfontein district, Mountain View farm (-29.03, 26.23); Faur-smith district, Boschrand farm-29.93, 24.80); Fauresmith district, Kalkfontein Dam (-29.52, 25.27); Jagersfontein district, Klein Preezfontein farm (-29.82, 25.42); Luckhoff district, Bankfontein farm (-29.73, 24.77); Philippolis district, Driekop (-30.49, 25.43); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Zastron district, Opnek farm (-30.27, 27.20). **Gaut- eng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Johannesburg (-26.20, 28.04); Johannes- burg, Auckland Park (-26.2, 28.04); KwaMhlanga (-25.42, 28.70); Pretoria/Tshwane, Arcadia (-25.74, 28.22); Pretoria/Tshwane, Lynnwood (-25.75, 28.25). **Limpopo:** Dendron, Amster- dam farm (-23.37, 29.32); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Northern Cape:** Akkerendam Nature Reserve (-31.43, 19.78); Calvinia (-31.46, 19.77); Kakamas (-28.76, 20.61); Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park (-25.48, 20.24); Kim- berley (-28.73, 24.76); Kuruman district, Dithakong tribal land (-27.13, 23.94); Meerkat National Park (-30.77, 21.24); Namaqua National Park (-30.01, 17.58); Prieska district, Remhoogte farm (-29.53, 23.00); Richtersveld National Park, Akkedis Pass (-28.18, 17.04); Riemvasmaak (-28.45, 20.31); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Tankwa Karoo Nation- al Park, Steenkampshoek (-32.28, 20.16). **North West:** Kgawane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Caledon (-23.83, 27.95); Laingsburg District, Wagendrift Lodge (-33.38, 20.91).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling species that was mainly sampled by hand from rocks, grass tussocks, short shrubs and the soil surface. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Savanna, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011, Haddad *et al.*, 2013). It was also sampled from pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Figs 1–10. *Icius insolidus*. 1–3. Female. 4–6. Male. 7, 8. Epigynes. 9, 10. Male palp. Credits: 1–3, 5, 7, 9. Charles Haddad. 4. Vida van der Walt. 6, 10. From Wesołowska (1999). 8. From Wesołowska (1999).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No threats. Protected in >10 reserves and parks.

TAXONOMY: Redescribed Wesołowska (2006).

Icius jacksoni Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024

COMMON NAME: Jackson's Icius Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic species described in 2024 and known only from the male and type locality (EEO= <100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 912 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Richtersveld National Park, Sendelingsdrift camp (-28.12, 16.59).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling species

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the female

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only the male is known (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024).

Icius jacksoni
Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024

Figs 1–4. *Icius jacksoni* male. 1, 2. Habitus. 3, 4. Male palp. Credits: From Haddad & Wesolowska (2024).

Icius nigricaudus Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009

COMMON NAME: Black-tailed Icius Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An endemic species described in 2009 from Ndumo Game Reserve (EOO=2 537 km²; AOO=20 km²; 30–405 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<5 000 km²), more sampling is needed to determine its range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile farm (-26.90, 32.32); Ndumo Game Reserve, E shore of Shokwe Pan (-26.88, 32.21); Ndumo Game Reserve, SW shore of Banzi Pan (-26.89, 32.28); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Mpumalanga*: Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94).

LIFESTYLE: This rare species was collected from the base of grasses in wetland habitats in the Savanna Biome. Several specimens were also collected from under bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* (Haddad, 2016). This species somewhat resembles *Crematogaster* ants in colour and size.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is known from three protected areas: Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad, 2016), Ophathe Game Reserve and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al., 2010), but more sampling is needed to determine range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009).

Figs 1–9. *Icius nigricaudus*. 1–5. Male. 6. Female. 7, 8. Epigynes. 9. Male palp. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4, 5, 7, 9. From Wesolowska & Haddad (2009). 6, 8. Charles Haddad.

Icius pulchellus Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011

COMMON NAME: Black-striped Icius Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2011 and known from two provinces. The distribution of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.59, 25.45). **Northern Cape:** Namaqua National Park (-30.02, 17.58); Port Nolloth, Happy Valley Beach (-29.29, 16.87); Tankwa Karoo National Park (-32.28, 19.82).

LIFESTYLE: Specimens were collected by pitfall trapping, hand collecting from rocks and beating low shrubs in the Succulent Karoo and Grassland biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. It is conserved in three protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011, 2024).

Figs 1–12. *Icius pulchellus*. 1, 2, 5, 6. Female. 3, 4, 7. Male. 8–10. Epigyne. 11, 12. Male palp. Credits: 1–4. Vida van der Walt. 5–9, 11. Charles Haddad. 10. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2024). 12. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2011).

GENUS *IRANATTUS* Prószyński, 1992

The genus *Iranattus* is known from two species (World Spider Catalog, 2023), and only one of these is known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Iranattus jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Iranattus rectangularis* Prószyński, 1992

MORPHOLOGY: Size: 4–5 mm. Carapace rounded, very wide, relatively high, especially posteriorly; posterior eyes situated on small tubercles; carapace dark brown, with fawn setae on slopes, brown bristles near eyes, anterior eyes surrounded by orange-fawn scales; clypeus with long fawn setae; chelicerae brown; maxillae brown with pale tips, labium and sternum brown. Abdomen elongated, distinctly narrower than carapace, blackish with numerous short dense grey hairs; ventrally dark; spinnerets greyish. Legs brown, with the distal ends of their segments darker; femora III are almost twice as long as the others.

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dweller; one species was sampled from the flood debris on a riverbank.

TAXONOMY: *Iranattus* is considered a senior synonym of *Monomotapa* Wesolowska, 1999.

Figs 1–2. *Iranattus principalis*, dorsal and lateral view. From Wesolowska (1999).

Iranattus principalis Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Iranattus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1999 from Zimbabwe. Recorded from three other African countries. In South Africa, it is known from Limpopo (EOO= <1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 605–894 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, Nigeria, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Soutpansberg, Stoke farm (-22.48, 29.88).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living wanderer sampled with pitfall traps in the Savanna Biome. This species was confined to savannah habitats in the Ivory Coast, where it was collected on the branches of shrubs.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide geographical range and is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Wesolowska (1999) and the female by Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2022).

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